

A New Realistic Approach for the Relay Node Placement Problem in Wireless Sensor Networks by Means of Evolutionary Computation

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At present, the use of the wireless sensor networks is increasing considerably, in more and more fields of application. This encourages many researchers to try to overcome the disadvantages of this type of network. This paper focuses on how to add and place relay nodes to a static wireless sensor network in order to optimize three important factors not considered jointly before in any paper found in the existing literature: energy consumption, average coverage and network reliability. To this end, we tackle a np-hard multiobjective optimization problem using two genetic algorithms (NSGA-II and SPEA2) chosen from evolutionary computation. The quality of the results obtained is measured by means of two multiobjective indicators (hypervolume and set coverage). All the results obtained are analyzed in depth using a widespread statistical methodology. We conclude that SPEA2 provides better performance on average than NSGA-II, and furthermore that the addition of relay nodes is a good way to optimize traditional wireless sensor networks.

Key words: wireless sensor network, router, relay node, coverage, energy consumption, reliability, multiobjective optimization, evolutionary computation, NSGA-II, SPEA2, hypervolume, set coverage.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The technology of Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) [6] is one of the most important emerging areas at present in wireless communications. This is evidenced by the high number of applications that we can find, both in civil (precision agriculture, environmental control, vigilance and security, industrial process monitoring, and forest fire detection, among many others) and in military areas (battlefield surveillance and rescue operations) [22].

WSNs are traditionally composed of a set of sensors that measure physical variables of its environment, and a sink node that collects all the captured information. There are some important factors that encourage the use of WSNs, such as their low-cost devices and the absence of wires, which facilitates the deployment of the network. These factors, among others, allow the use of WSNs in environments where the deployment of other networks would be very expensive or impossible. However, this kind of network also has shortcomings that affect features like Quality of Service (QoS) and energy costs.

Usually, the sensors are powered by batteries to avoid the use of wires; consequently, WSNs are particularly sensitive to energy consumption, which directly affects the network QoS. Each time a sensor captures some data, it has to send this information to the sink node, which involves an energy cost. This energy consumption is similar in all devices in networks with a star topology. However, nowadays WSNs have a multi-hop topology, so the energy cost suffered by each sensor is different: it depends on the information received and the data sent to the sink node. This situation involves the existence of bottlenecks, i.e. sensors that are subjected to a higher energy cost. Recently, a new kind of device specialized in communication tasks and called router or relay node was added to WSNs to try to avoid these bottlenecks [28] [19].

The efficient design of a traditional WSN depends on many factors, even more if it includes routers. This is the reason why efficient WSN deployment has been defined as a np-hard [10] optimization problem [2] [3], which can only be tackled by certain approaches that we explain in the next Section.

In this paper we consider how to optimize a previously-established static WSN by adding relay nodes, taking into account three important factors: energy consumption, coverage provided and network reliability. For this purpose we used non-conventional computational techniques in order to solve this np-hard optimization problem, specifically two well-known Genetic Algorithms (GAs) widely used in Evolutionary Computation (EC) [32].

In the course of this work, we make the following contributions: 1) The relay node placement problem was solved using two multiobjective evolution-

ary algorithms (MOEAs): NSGA-II [8] and SPEA2 [33]. 2) Three important features (energy consumption, coverage and reliability) not considered before in any paper found were simultaneously optimized, which implies that ours is a more realistic approach. 3) We used our own data set, freely available [15], which means that this work can be replicated and improved by other authors. 4) In order to determine the quality of the results obtained, we used two well-known multiobjective measures (hypervolume [31] and set coverage [32]), as well as our own indicator which shows the advantages that the inclusion of routers in a traditional WSN provides. 5) Finally, all the results obtained were analyzed in depth through a widely used statistical methodology.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. In Section 2 we discuss the related work. Next, we define the relay node placement optimization problem. Some important aspects of np-hard optimization problems are shown in Section 4. In Section 5 we explain the multiobjective metaheuristics used to solve the problem. The experimental results are discussed in Section 6. Finally, our concluding remarks appear in Section 7.

2 RELATED WORK

We find two main lines of research for WSNs in the literature: on the one hand, works that study how to optimize the deployment of traditional WSNs (a set of sensors and a collector node); on the other hand, works that study how to optimize these traditional WSNs by adding relay nodes. We present a detailed study of these approaches in the supplementary file available online.

Several heuristics and EC algorithms consider the first approach, with a common disadvantage: they use a higher number of nodes than the needed for optimizing the energy consumption, so the network costs are greater.

The works taking the second approach try to overcome this disadvantage by including relay nodes. Our work follows this line, where we use two EC algorithms (NSGA-II and SPEA2) simultaneously optimizing three important factors, enhancing so previous works [17] with lesser realism and objectives.

We would wish to compare our results against other approaches, but we have not found any free-access testbed that fits this problem definition. Most authors use randomly generated or non-public data sets [30] [23], where both energy model and fitness functions are different. Therefore we propose our own testbed [15], freely available to allow the replication and enhancement of our research. We focused our comparisons on studying how WSN performance is affected by adding routers, comparing the results obtained from our optimization problem against the fitness values without using them.

3 DEFINITION OF THE RELAY NODE PLACEMENT PROBLEM

In this paper we consider a WSN composed of several wireless devices: N routers, M sensors and a sink node (Fig. 1). All devices are placed on a 2D-surface of size $D_x \times D_y$, where only those which are at a distance lower than R_c can be linked directly. D_x , D_y and R_c are real values.

FIGURE 1 Representation of the wireless sensor network considered in this work.

Simultaneously and periodically, all the sensors capture information about the environment with a sensibility radius $R_s \in \mathbb{R}^+$. This information must immediately be sent to the sink node, which collects all the information captured by the sensors. The routing protocol used is based on the minimum path among devices provided by Dijkstra's algorithm [5]. In addition, we suppose a perfect synchronization, as well as a perfect medium access as defined by $S-MAC$ [29] which ensures that there will be no collisions among devices.

The sensors are usually powered by batteries, hence their lifetimes will depend on the energy expenditure. When a sensor sends a packet to the collector node, it is likely that this path involves several devices. If this packet arrives at a sensor, this device will send it on to the collector node, which involves an energy cost. The routers or relay nodes are devices specialized in communication tasks with higher energy capacities than sensors; they are included to reduce the sensor workload, carrying out these packet retransmissions. In this paper, both collector node and routers have an unlimited power supply.

We have used a well-known energy model [13] for the energy expenditure suffered by the sensors, where the transmission power that a sensor i needs to reach another device j (sensor, router or collector) is defined as

$$P_i = \beta \cdot d_{i,j}^\alpha \mid d_{i,j} < R_c \quad (1)$$

for $i = 1, 2, \dots, M$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, M + N + 1$

where $d_{i,j}$ is the distance between i and j , $\alpha \in [2, 4]$ is the path loss exponent and $\beta > 0$ is the transmission quality parameter. Initially, sensors have the same energy charge (EC), decreasing over time because of sending packets. Accordingly, the residual energy of a sensor i at time t is given by

$$E_i(t) = E_i(t-1) - [(r_i(t) + 1) \cdot P_i \cdot amp \cdot K] \quad (2)$$

for $i = 1, 2, \dots, M$ and $t > 0$

where amp is the energy consumption per bit of the power amplifier, K is the information packet size, $r_i(t)$ is the number of incoming packets that sensor i receives from other devices at time t (and that it must send to the collector node), and the $+1$ term is because i captures a packet at this time and then this sensor must send it too. As occurs in other papers and as we can see here, the energy expenditure depends only on the sending tasks; in other words the receiving, processing and sensing tasks are considered negligible.

We have studied in previous works how to optimize a network taking into account two important factors: the average energy consumption and the coverage area [17]. Now, in this work we propose a third important factor that provides a higher realism to this problem definition: *network reliability*.

Prior to defining these factors, it is necessary to understand the lifetime concept. The lifetime (LF) is the number of time units over which a network is able to provide enough information about its environment. A coverage threshold (CV) is often used for this purpose; whereby the coverage percentage offered by the sensors must be higher than this threshold. Below, the fitness functions corresponding to the factors that we optimize are defined:

- Average energy consumption (AEC , to minimize). This is the average energy consumption of the sensors over the network lifetime. Its unit of measure is the Joule (J). The fitness function is defined as

$$f_1 = LF^{-1} \cdot \sum_{t=1}^{LF} \sum_{i=1}^M \left(\frac{E_i(t-1) - E_i(t)}{sAlive(t)} \right) \quad (3)$$

where $sAlive(t)$ is the number of sensors with $E(t) > 0$ at time $t > 0$.

- Average coverage (AC , to maximize). Average coverage offered by the sensors over the network lifetime. We find two ways to obtain this coverage [27]. On the one hand, the coverage provided by a sensor is the area of a circumference of radius R_s , hence the global coverage is the intersection of the M sensors. On the other hand, a boolean matrix of $D_x \times D_y$ points can be used, in which all points that are inside the sensibility radius of some sensors will be activated, so the activated points are counted. In this paper, we have opted for the second method; although the first is more precise, the second is simpler to compute. In (4), R is the boolean matrix and R_{xy} is row x and column y of R .

$$f_2 = LF^{-1} \cdot \sum_{t=1}^{LF} \sum_{x=1}^{D_x} \sum_{y=1}^{D_y} \left(\frac{R_{xy}}{D_x \cdot D_y} \right) \quad (4)$$

- Network reliability (NR , to maximize). Average network fault-tolerance representing the probability that each sensor can successfully send its captured data to the collector. Let $Re(i)$ be the reliability of a sensor [7] (5), where P is the number of disjoint paths between the sensor i and the collector node, h_l is the number of hops in the l -th disjoint path, and Err is the local channel error. The number of disjoint paths between two nodes is calculated by solving the minimum flow problem using Suurballe's Algorithm [26]. In this manner, the average network reliability is defined in (6), where $Re(i)$ is given by (5).

$$Re(i) = 1 - \prod_{l=1}^P (1 - (1 - Err)^{h_l}) \quad for \ i = 1, 2, \dots, M \quad (5)$$

$$f_3 = \sum_{i=1}^M \left(\frac{Re(i)}{M} \right) \quad (6)$$

Summarizing, we have defined the np-hard optimization problem consisting of the scenario dimension ($D_x \times D_y$), the communication and sensibility radius (R_c and R_s respectively), the initial energy charge of the sensors (EC), the information packet size (K), the threshold coverage (CV), the path loss exponent (α), the energy consumption per bit of the power amplifier (amp), the transmission quality parameter (β), the local channel error (Err), the positions of the collector node (C), the M sensors and the N routers. This np-hard optimization problem requires non-conventional methodologies to solve it in a reasonable computation time, as we will address below.

TABLE 1
Data set used in this paper.

$WSN(\text{routers})$	$D_x \times D_y$	M	R_c	$HO-AEC$	$HO-AC$	$HO-NR$
100x100_15_30	100x100	15	30	0.1091	89.24%	95.67%
200x200_15_30	200x200	57	30	0.2791	87.10%	93.23%
300x300_15_30	300x300	128	30	0.4225	76.44%	85.28%

4 NP-HARD MULTIOBJECTIVE OPTIMIZATION PROBLEMS AND METAHEURISTICS

There are two kinds of np-hard optimization problems [32]: Single Optimization Problems (SOP) where a single objective is optimized; and Multiobjective Optimization Problems (MOP), where several ones are optimized. Most problems in the real world are MOP, including the one we tackle in this paper. In the supplementary file, available online, MOP is explained in depth, providing some important metrics to evaluate the quality of the results.

In a MOP the objectives are in conflict, so we cannot find a decision vector that simultaneously optimizes all the fitness functions. Instead, we obtain a set of optimal solutions, also called the optimal non-dominated set, where its image is known as the optimal Pareto front or frontier. A solution is said to be Pareto Optimal if and only if it is non-dominated by other solutions; in other words, if there is not any solution that enhances any objective without worsening another one. This is the Pareto dominance concept.

When we use a SOP, it is easy to evaluate the quality of the results, since we only need to compare them with a reference value. However, when we use a MOP, a set of non-dominated solutions are obtained, and then we need to establish the quality of this Pareto front. For this purpose, there are two important multiobjective performance metrics: hypervolume and set coverage.

There are several approaches to solve np-hard optimization problems in a reasonable computing time, being EC the most widely used which is based on biological evolution [1], providing good solutions in a reduced computation time. We can distinguish an important set of techniques in *EC*: Evolutionary Algorithms (*EAs*), which are population-based algorithms that use mechanisms from the Darwin's theory of evolution such as mutation, survival of the best individuals, reproduction and so on. This way, we considered a pair of well-known metaheuristics (methodologies to solve very general kind of problems) belonging to *EAs*: NSGA-II and SPEA2. These algorithms

belong to a subtype of *EAs* called Genetic Algorithms (*GAs*), which are characterized by encoding their individuals as chromosomes or arrays. The encoding that we used to represent a solution to this problem is straightforward: a chromosome is a 2D-coordinate list of M routers (Fig. 1).

The details about NSGA-II and SPEA2 algorithms, as well as the performance metrics, can be found in the supplementary file available online.

5 EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

Next we show the experiments and results for solving the relay node placement problem using two multiobjective genetic algorithms to optimize three factors: average energy consumption, average coverage and reliability.

5.1 Experimental Data Sets

As no testbed fitting the problem was found, we defined a customized one, freely available [15]. This experimental data set is composed of three scenarios of different size (Table 1), where a number of sensors and a collector node are placed. Each scenario represents a traditional static WSN with the minimum number of sensors required to cover the whole surface. Thus, if a sensor covers a circumference of radius R_s and the scenario area is a rectangle of dimensions $D_x \times D_y$, then the number of sensors (M) is:

$$M = \lceil (D_x \times D_y) / (\pi \times R_s^2) \rceil \quad (7)$$

The WSNs of the data set were generated using a mono-objective EA where we optimized the coverage offered by the sensors, taking as our stop condition the attainment of 90% coverage. As we said in Section 3, it is necessary to define some important parameters: $R_c = 30m$ and $R_s = 15m$ from [21], $K = 128KB$, $CV = 70\%$, $e = 10\%$, and several energy parameters ($EC = 5J$, $\alpha = 2$, $\beta = 1$ and $amp = 100pJ/bit/m^2$) from [14]. In former works, we used these scenarios with $R_c = 30m$ and $R_c = 60m$; however, it makes no sense to consider $R_c = 60m$ for the current problem, since the network reliability is almost 100% for all the cases due to the large number of paths between the sensors and the collector node that this R_c value provides.

5.2 Experimentation

We optimized the WSNs adding routers, taking into account that including routers increases the network cost; hence we decided not to include more than 20% of these devices. Thus we defined 10 different cases, two for the

TABLE 2
Median hypervolume and standard deviation for each test case.

<i>NSGA-II</i>					
<i>WSN(routers)</i>	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000
100x100.15_30(2)	41.01% 0.0030	41.25% 0.0024	41.47% 0.0002	41.48% 0.0001	41.48% 0.0000
100x100.15_30(3)	53.54% 0.0050	54.15% 0.0018	54.46% 0.0019	54.56% 0.0011	54.63% 0.0005
200x200.15_30(2)	32.49% 0.0100	33.22% 0.0042	33.53% 0.0025	33.64% 0.0018	33.74% 0.0021
200x200.15_30(4)	41.46% 0.0180	43.21% 0.0167	45.07% 0.0109	45.57% 0.0134	45.96% 0.0116
200x200.15_30(6)	48.75% 0.0345	53.12% 0.0193	55.65% 0.0161	57.00% 0.0168	57.68% 0.0156
200x200.15_30(9)	57.14% 0.0254	61.82% 0.0223	65.57% 0.0211	67.45% 0.0194	68.31% 0.0174
300x300.15_30(6)	28.35% 0.0074	29.44% 0.0068	30.42% 0.0061	30.81% 0.0060	31.05% 0.0057
300x300.15_30(12)	29.84% 0.0068	31.53% 0.0100	32.86% 0.0098	33.81% 0.0107	34.37% 0.0112
300x300.15_30(18)	31.26% 0.0061	32.92% 0.0088	34.30% 0.0107	34.99% 0.0097	35.41% 0.0099
300x300.15_30(24)	33.40% 0.0060	34.99% 0.0137	36.51% 0.0157	37.22% 0.0133	37.86% 0.0132
<i>SPEA2</i>					
<i>WSN(routers)</i>	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000
100x100.15_30(2)	41.07% 0.0021	41.24% 0.0016	41.31% 0.0015	41.46% 0.0002	41.46% 0.0002
100x100.15_30(3)	53.76% 0.0038	54.27% 0.0029	54.56% 0.0011	54.61% 0.0007	54.64% 0.0007
200x200.15_30(2)	32.56% 0.0054	32.88% 0.0053	33.21% 0.0032	33.38% 0.0031	33.47% 0.0026
200x200.15_30(4)	42.41% 0.0150	44.03% 0.0148	45.03% 0.0153	45.54% 0.0141	45.72% 0.0130
200x200.15_30(6)	53.35% 0.0180	55.98% 0.0179	57.53% 0.0072	58.57% 0.0124	59.09% 0.0084
200x200.15_30(9)	61.49% 0.0179	65.42% 0.0200	67.85% 0.0184	68.99% 0.0165	69.70% 0.0132
300x300.15_30(6)	29.45% 0.0062	30.55% 0.0071	31.19% 0.0072	31.54% 0.0068	31.78% 0.0055
300x300.15_30(12)	31.58% 0.0071	33.19% 0.0106	34.62% 0.0116	35.41% 0.0113	36.00% 0.0115
300x300.15_30(18)	33.44% 0.0089	35.22% 0.0086	36.73% 0.0092	37.68% 0.0080	38.34% 0.0093
300x300.15_30(24)	35.43% 0.0077	37.04% 0.0094	38.63% 0.0076	39.45% 0.0082	40.20% 0.0093

100x100 scenario (2 and 3 routers), and four for the remaining two (2, 4, 6 and 9 in the 200x200 scenario; and 6, 12, 18, and 24 in the 300x300 scenario).

A normal population size of 100 individuals was used for the two EAs considered. The stop criterion was the number of evaluations, since it is a criterion independent of the computer used, fairer than other criteria such as elapsed time. Thus we have considered five different numbers of evaluations (from 50 000 to 400 000) to observe the convergence of the algorithms; these values were arrived at experimentally, being enough to obtain good results.

We have tuned the parameters of the algorithms before starting the experiments, using a widespread strategy: starting from initial values, a parameter is selected on which to perform a parametric sweep, and then its value is fixed in its best configuration; next, another parameter is selected [16], and so on. Following this methodology, SPEA2 has a mutation of 70% and a crossover of 60%, and NSGA-II has a value of 80% for both parameters.

5.3 Results

The average hypervolume for each scenario, number of routers used, stop criterion and algorithm, and its standard deviation (*hypervolume*%*deviation*) are shown in Table 2. We obtained these values using 31 independent runs for statistical validity (30 runs is a quite typical number [11]). The reference

TABLE 3
Reference points used to obtain the hypervolume measure for each scenario.

$WSN(\text{routers})$	Ref AEC		Ref AC		Ref NR	
	<i>ideal</i>	<i>nadir</i>	<i>ideal</i>	<i>nadir</i>	<i>ideal</i>	<i>nadir</i>
100x100.15_30	0.02	0.1	100%	60%	100%	50%
200x200.15_30	0.10	0.30	100%	60%	100%	50%
300x300.15_30	0.04	0.50	100%	60%	100%	50%

values used to obtain the hypervolumes are listed in Table 3.

It is important to determine what kind of average value should be used: mean or median. For this purpose, we used the Shapiro–Wilk’s [25] and Kolmogrov–Smirnov–Lilliefors’s [18] tests with the following hypothesis: H_0 if data come from a normal distribution, and H_1 if not. We obtained a p-value lower than 0.05 for all the cases, so we cannot assume that data follow a normal distribution; therefore, we must use the *median* as average value.

TABLE 4
P-values obtained through Wilcoxon–Mann–Whitney’s test in order to compare performance between SPEA2 and NSGA-II using for this purpose the hypervolume indicator. P-values higher than 0.05 are shadow.

$WSN(\text{routers})$	SPEA2 vs NSGA-II				
	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000
100x100.15_30(2)	0.2505	0.9060	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
100x100.15_30(3)	0.0486	0.0182	0.0188	0.0370	0.1032
200x200.15_30(2)	0.3920	0.9938	0.9999	0.9995	0.9999
200x200.15_30(4)	0.0273	0.0410	0.5530	0.6136	0.7949
200x200.15_30(6)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0001	0.0001
200x200.15_30(9)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0008	0.0005
300x300.15_30(6)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
300x300.15_30(12)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
300x300.15_30(18)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
300x300.15_30(24)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000

If we observe the median hypervolumes (Table 2), sometimes one algorithm seems to provide better results than another, but we do not know if these differences are significant. With the aim of finding the best algorithmic behaviour, and in line with our previous test (the data do not follow a normal distribution and moreover the samples are independent), we used the

TABLE 5

For each test case, the algorithm with better performance is shown, according to the Wilcoxon–Mann–Whitney’s test.

$WSN(\text{routers})$	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000
100x100.15_30(2)	NONE	NONE	NSGA-II	NSGA-II	NSGA-II
100x100.15_30(3)	SPEA2	SPEA2	SPEA2	SPEA2	NONE
200x200.15_30(2)	NONE	NSGA-II	NSGA-II	NSGA-II	NSGA-II
200x200.15_30(4)	SPEA2	SPEA2	NONE	NONE	NONE
200x200.15_30(6)	SPEA2	SPEA2	SPEA2	SPEA2	SPEA2
200x200.15_30(9)	SPEA2	SPEA2	SPEA2	SPEA2	SPEA2
300x300.15_30(6)	SPEA2	SPEA2	SPEA2	SPEA2	SPEA2
300x300.15_30(12)	SPEA2	SPEA2	SPEA2	SPEA2	SPEA2
300x300.15_30(18)	SPEA2	SPEA2	SPEA2	SPEA2	SPEA2
300x300.15_30(24)	SPEA2	SPEA2	SPEA2	SPEA2	SPEA2

Wilcoxon–Mann–Whitney’s test [20] with the following hypotheses: H_0 if SPEA2 provides worse results than NSGA-II and H_1 if SPEA2 does not provide worse results than NSGA-II. Table 4 lists the p-values obtained, where values higher than 0.05 are shaded. Thus we observe that SPEA2 provides better performance in more complex scenarios, whereas NSGA-II is better in simpler ones. Moreover, in some cases there are not significant differences between the algorithms (scenarios of average complexity). Table 5 reflects these conclusions, where we see which algorithm is better in each case.

We used another multiobjective measure too: set coverage. We compared the coverage relation among median fronts obtained from the 31 independent runs previously carried out. Table 6 confirms that SPEA2 has better global average coverage (62.68%) than NSGA-II (27.46%). We can reach the same conclusions as for hypervolume: SPEA2 provides better results in more complex scenarios, while NSGA-II is better in simpler ones. However, SPEA2 is better on average. The number of non-dominated solutions is important when the quality of a front is evaluated. Accordingly, for each instance and algorithm we observe in Table 7 the number of non-dominated solutions of the median Pareto front from the 31 independent runs with 400 000 evaluations. Note that the algorithm that provides the best significant performance for each instance provides the greatest number of non-dominated solutions in general; however, such algorithm does not imply that these are the best ones, which is why it must be supplemented by another measure such as set coverage (Table 6). The two metrics taken together, number of non-dominated solutions and set coverage, give us an idea of the appearance of the fronts.

Figure 2 shows this behavior in two different instances. We used four

TABLE 6
Coverage relation between NSGA-II and SPEA2 for each test case.

<i>WSN(routers)</i>	<i>C (NSGA-II,SPEA2)</i>				
	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000
100x100_15_30(2)	45.60%	23.71%	66.56%	84.40%	96.03%
100x100_15_30(3)	43.81%	25.91%	36.56%	46.87%	46.59%
200x200_15_30(2)	40.00%	40.44%	57.37%	44.77%	63.60%
200x200_15_30(4)	25.44%	68.93%	9.92%	68.79%	42.18%
200x200_15_30(6)	0.00%	4.49%	0.00%	38.19%	42.52%
200x200_15_30(9)	0.00%	19.15%	1.11%	9.21%	0.00%
300x300_15_30(6)	7.04%	54.78%	8.29%	3.14%	15.09%
300x300_15_30(12)	0.00%	3.80%	46.61%	1.08%	7.97%
300x300_15_30(18)	10.00%	3.77%	6.56%	6.49%	16.67%
300x300_15_30(24)	21.95%	22.00%	5.26%	23.81%	16.67%
Partial average	19.38%	26.70%	23.83%	32.68%	34.73%
Average			27.46%		
<i>WSN(routers)</i>	<i>C (SPEA2,NSGA-II)</i>				
	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000
100x100_15_30(2)	69.34%	76.59%	63.49%	87.61%	82.04%
100x100_15_30(3)	20.08%	32.42%	25.95%	29.76%	57.29%
200x200_15_30(2)	43.48%	62.09%	35.09%	34.43%	39.16%
200x200_15_30(4)	44.44%	7.24%	78.57%	29.51%	58.66%
200x200_15_30(6)	96.61%	87.59%	87.09%	55.98%	61.11%
200x200_15_30(9)	93.75%	66.67%	86.11%	41.18%	99.25%
300x300_15_30(6)	66.10%	20.00%	87.70%	80.68%	50.98%
300x300_15_30(12)	95.24%	84.78%	22.03%	95.76%	60.00%
300x300_15_30(18)	68.09%	87.27%	68.89%	68.33%	86.30%
300x300_15_30(24)	65.00%	57.89%	79.55%	46.30%	90.32%
Partial average	66.21%	58.25%	63.45%	56.95%	68.51%
Average			62.68%		

TABLE 7
Execution times and number of non-dominated solutions for each algorithm for 400 000 evaluations.

<i>WSN(routers)</i>	NSGA-II		SPEA-2	
	Time(s)	Solutions	Time(s)	Solutions
100x100_15_30(2)	6450.00	587	6616.67	546
100x100_15_30(3)	7440.00	244	7911.33	509
200x200_15_30(2)	7700.00	207	7633.33	150
200x200_15_30(4)	8950.00	126	9348.67	228
200x200_15_30(6)	10200.00	59	10753.33	121
200x200_15_30(9)	10900.00	32	12460.00	50
300x300_15_30(6)	15800.00	59	16190.91	71
300x300_15_30(12)	16600.00	42	17633.33	39
300x300_15_30(18)	17000.00	47	18600.00	60
300x300_15_30(24)	18000.00	20	20166.67	41

different representations to understand the 3D fronts. We only show the two biggest scenarios with the greatest number of routers.

FIGURE 2
 Median Pareto fronts obtained from NSGA-II and SPEA-2 for 400 000 evaluations.
 (a) Instance 200x200_15_30(9) (b) Instance 300x300_15_30(24)

TABLE 8

Extreme values of median Pareto fronts from 31 independent runs for each WSN and stop criterion of 400 000 evaluations (NSGA-II with dark shading and SPEA2 lighter)

WSN(routers)	AEC		AC		NR	
	best	worst	best	worst	best	worst
100x100.15_30(2)	0.0570 -47.80%	0.0692 -36.60%	91.56% 2.60%	87.64% -1.79%	98.59% 3.05%	96.42% 0.78%
100x100.15_30(3)	0.0442 -59.49%	0.0596 -45.37%	91.55% 2.59%	84.51% -5.30%	99.15% 3.64%	98.11% 2.55%
200x200.15_30(2)	0.1980 -29.05%	0.2377 -14.85%	88.77% 1.92%	85.46% -1.88%	94.90% 1.79%	93.38% 0.16%
200x200.15_30(4)	0.1717 -38.48%	0.2276 -18.45%	89.12% 2.32%	85.86% -1.43%	95.52% 2.46%	94.13% 0.97%
200x200.15_30(6)	0.1448 -48.12%	0.2015 -27.81%	90.15% 3.50%	86.43% -0.76%	96.12% 3.09%	94.56% 1.43%
200x200.15_30(9)	0.1192 -57.28%	0.2222 -20.39%	89.46% 2.71%	83.60% -4.02%	96.43% 3.43%	94.88% 1.77%
300x300.15_30(9)	0.2522 -40.31%	0.3451 -18.32%	87.71% 14.75%	78.01% 2.05%	91.02% 6.73%	85.91% 0.74%
300x300.15_30(12)	0.2415 -42.84%	0.3437 -18.66%	88.08% 15.22%	78.96% 3.30%	91.62% 7.44%	89.54% 5.00%
300x300.15_30(18)	0.2348 -44.43%	0.3580 -15.27%	87.83% 14.90%	75.97% -0.62%	92.49% 8.45%	86.02% 0.87%
300x300.15_30(24)	0.2161 -48.85%	0.3527 -16.52%	87.95% 15.06%	75.91% -0.70%	92.77% 8.79%	86.29% 1.18%

Up to this point, we have analyzed these algorithms in multiobjective terms, using both set coverage and hypervolume indicators. Now, we are going to study the gains in fitness values from including relay nodes. We took the extreme values of median Pareto fronts from the 31 independent runs for each WSN, using a stop criterion of 400 000 evaluations. Next, we compared these fitness values with the values obtained from the same WSNs without relay nodes (traditional WSNs). These values, called TR -AEC, TR -AC and TR -NR, are listed in Table 1. The best and worst values for each fitness function are placed in Table 8, where each of them includes a quality indicator in the form $fitnessValue_{quality}$. This indicator shows the percentage by which a fitness value is increased (positive) or decreased (negative) in relation to its TR value (Table 1). These values are taken from the algorithm (NSGA-II or SPEA2) that provides the better performance in each case (Table 5). Accordingly the values from NSGA-II have been given a dark shading and values from SPEA2 a clear one. We have decided to use SPEA2 values for the cases where there are not significant differences between the algorithms (because it provides better results on average). Thus, for example, we can see in this table that AEC has been decreased by up to 59.49%, AC increases by up to 15.22% and NR increases by up to 8.79%, so we clearly observe that the inclusion of relay nodes in a static WSN is a good way to optimize it.

Average execution times (in seconds) for each algorithm for 400 000 evaluations are showed in Table 7. We see according that as the scenario dimensions and the number of routers are increased, the complexity of the problem is increased as well, and so too the required computational effort.

Finally, we provide some implementation details. Both algorithms and problem definition were programmed by ourselves in C++, using for graphs the Lemon library (<http://lemon.cs.elte.hu>). We used the IBM SPSS software (<http://www-01.ibm.com/software/es/analytics/spss>) to calculate the *Shapiro-Wilk's* and *Kolmogrov-Smirnov-Lilliefors's* tests. The *Wilcoxon–Mann – Whitney's* test and hypervolume were taken from [9]. All experiments were performed on an AMD Opteron 6176 2.3Ghz under an operating system Scientific Linux 6.2, using the 4.4.5 version of the GCC compiler for C++.

6 CONCLUDING REMARKS

We used EC to solve a MOP with the aid of two well-known MOEAs: NSGA-II and SPEA2. The optimization problem is an efficient network deployment by means of the addition of relay nodes to a previously-established static traditional WSN. We considered three important features to be optimized simultaneously: average coverage, network reliability and energy consumption.

No public data set was found that fit this problem, hence we decided to define our own experimental instance, making it available to the scientific community. Thus other authors would be able to replicate or continue our research (with other metaheuristics, for example). In addition, and with the same aim of facilitating the study of our research, we used two standard multiobjective measures: hypervolume and set coverage.

We analyzed the results obtained using a widely used statistical methodology. The main conclusion from these results is that SPEA2 provides a significantly better performance than NSGA-II for complex scenarios, but NSGA-II is better in simpler ones. Moreover, we studied the advantages provided by the addition of routers to traditional WSNs as an optimization method; in this respect, we conclude that this methodology is a good way to optimize WSNs, this conclusion being the main contribution of this paper.

As to future lines of research, we think that it would be very interesting to conduct real-world experiments in order to validate our hypotheses. To this end, we are working to obtain data sets that could be checked in the real world. This kind of experiment could be used to study the differences between theoretical energy models and real WSN communications.

Furthermore, other metaheuristics based on continuous optimization could be used, such as MOPSO[4], GSA[24] or ABC[12] from swarm intelligence algorithms. Our aim is to find an algorithm that provide good results in general terms, such that this algorithm could be used by the scientific community in the deployment of WSNs. To achieve this, it would be a good idea to con-

sider a greater number of synthetic instances which do not have to have a square shape, i.e. equal values of D_x and D_y . A further research interest is to use parallel computing techniques to tackle more complex data sets.

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